

ADOPTION OF DIGITAL PAYMENTS AMONG GLOBAL CONSUMERS A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The fast-paced evolution in digital technologies has been instrumental in bringing about a paradigm shift in the way financial transactions are carried out, resulting in a massive transition to digital payment methods. The pervasive connectivity offered by ICT has been instrumental in bringing about a major transformation in the financial market and its operations. Also, the tendency for digitization and utilization of the internet has brought in massive modifications to the way the economy around the world operates. The aim of this systematic review is to critically examine digital payment adoption among consumers globally. The idea is to synthesize prevalent literature to explain major factors that impacted patterns and trends in digital payment adoption. Overall, a total of 1454 studies were found out of which 22 studies were chosen after eliminating studies based on the inclusion and exclusion criterion. The findings from this study indicated that digital payments largely impacted economic growth over short-term periods but did not influence economic growth in the long run. Digital payments were also beneficial for commercial banks in terms of augmenting their productivity and profitability. In addition, based on the findings of the review, it was also noted that digital or electronic payments had a positive impact on productivity and business growth, mainly in the financial sector. However, from the findings it could also be understood that overall digital inclusivity within rural regions can only be enhanced with proper infrastructure, technical skills and literacy levels, and by improving connectivity.

Keywords: Business Growth, Digital Payments, Economic Growth, ICT, Productivity, Rural Development

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1. INTRODUCTION

Developments in the domain of information and communication technology (ICT) have transformed the way people live. Tremendous progress has been driven by digitization and ICT in the realms of marketing, finance and economic functioning [1]. With the advent of ICT and digital innovation, a major shift has also been observed across the world, where business-related transactions moved from liquid cash to digital [2]. Transactions in the present day are continuously changing from transactions that are based on cash to those that are based on digital technologies. The pervasive connectivity offered by ICT has been instrumental in bringing about a major transformation in the financial market and its operations [1]. Also, the tendency for digitization and utilization of the internet has brought in massive modifications to the way the economy around the world operates. The rise of an extensive array of financial technology applications allows consumers to shift across the traditional payment system that is cash-based. Gradually, digital payments have become the norm in the day-to-day lives of individuals. Such progressive developments within the financial sector have resulted in the introduction of several technologies for digital payment, based on which payees and payers leverage digital payment apps to receive as well as send money. Thus, the system of payments has transitioned from one that was paper and coin-based to digital payment techniques that are convenient, cost effective and fast [3].

A common definition of digital payment would be a medium that is utilized for facilitating monetary transactions for diverse services and goods purchased over the internet [4]. The current electronic or digital payment modes have turned out to be a significant payment medium that people and businesses are known to utilize as it offers a fast, secure and convenient mode of payment by leveraging the internet. Further, it also offers the economy a much-required opening for growth while excelling in techno-developments within the global economy [1]. Another aspect is that it is known largely facilitate e-commerce as they extensively rely on digital payments. Digital payments do not just offer e-businesses or e-commerce with advance money, but it also increases efficiency and reduce fraudulent activities while adding to innovations in the global payment systems [5].

In India, digital payments have been facilitated by the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI), which also includes the United Payments Interface (UPI), and Immediate Payment Service (IMPS). UPI allows individuals to create digital wallet accounts connected to their bank accounts in any bank across India. Digital money transfers are facilitated with UPI, for making payments at merchant outlets, for making payments towards utility services, and business payments as well. A growth of around 349% was observed in transaction volumes yearly, with transaction values growing by 45% each year to around \$18.9 billion during the financial year 2018-2019 [6]. Digital payments in China have reported a rate of penetration of around 90% among their users of mobile internet. Common apps in use would include TenPay (WeChat Pay) and Alipay which dominate the market having around 820 million users and 650 million users respectively. Even comparatively backward regions have embraced digital payment systems. Offline consumers are known to use Alipay and WeChat Pay for making payments at supermarkets, daily travel, catering, and entertainment [7]. As far as European regions are concerned, it reports a diversity in terms of digital payments. PayPal is the commonly used platform for making digital payments in Spain and Germany [8], while credit and debit cards are the modes of choice within France.

Across the Netherlands, iDEAL is the app that is used by individuals to make online purchases. iDEAL is a system of domestic transfer that is based on SEPA credit transfer and is duly endorsed by all Dutch banks [9]. Whereas, in the United Kingdom (UK), digital payments are supported with the Pingit app, used extensively at merchant outlets and it also allows e-commerce payments. Transfer of funds occurs by leveraging the UK Faster Payments service [10].

1.2. Problem Statement

In the rapidly advancing environment of business, the system of digital payments has come to play a key role. A large number of businesses as well as individuals have embraced digital payments. Several vital business initiatives and business transactions are now being converted into digital. This scenario is prevalent not only in developed nations but also in developing nations as well. Across the world, many individuals now conduct most of their transactions through digital mediums [11]. While people refrain from carrying cash anymore, they do possess smartphones and debit or credit cards. This is indicative of the fact that needs can be fulfilled even in the absence of physical cash, and business transactions can also be executed using available digital payment mediums or platforms.

International trade and global businesses have witnessed a rapid increase over a period of the past 20 to 30 years. The diaspora throughout the world has also driven an increment in payments across borders. With rapid developments in the domain of payment technology in recent times, there have been several scholars who have accorded much attention to digital payments, and there have been several studies [12][13][14] as well that have concentrated on the behaviour and willingness of digital payments, how digital payments make major impacts on diverse key industry sectors. Further, studies also exist which indicate that digital payments tend to alter the consumption behaviour of people [15]. Nonetheless, research pertaining to how digital payments are impacting economic growth, facilitating rural development, and entrepreneurial growth is scant in literature.

1.3. Significance of the Study

Digital payment systems enable businesses and entrepreneurs to make payments towards goods and services through an electronic format, with the help of a smartphone, retail point of sale, internet and other access points that are widely available rather than depending on hard currency or cheques [16]. For businesses and entrepreneurs, in developed markets, more so in developing markets, having an unfettered access to platforms for digital payment is more than a matter of convenience. For individuals who are commencing a business, it is possible to fasten the process of business registration with digital payments, while lowering the time usually taken for transferring payments for business permits and licenses. Furthermore, having adequate access to digital platforms could augment e-commerce participation [17]. It could also be beneficial in supply-chain management and also during interactions among vendors and clients. When businesses opt to transfer wages through electronic mediums, it tends to save time, lower costs, augment the level of transparency, and tends to empower employees by providing them with an account and access to financial services like loans. Businesses and entrepreneurs can develop a credit history that would enhance their capability to gain access to investment and working capital [18]. For entrepreneurs and business that operate at a large-scale level, digital applications such as e-filing of business, social benefits, and employee taxes could lower the costs associated with tax compliance. Given these factors, it becomes imperative to understand how digital payments impact the economy, businesses and entrepreneurs as such.

Providing insights into these aspects would not only be beneficial to individuals, businesses, and entrepreneurs but it would help them to obtain a detailed understanding about the same. This essentially outlines the significance of this review and the contribution it would make to economies and societies overall, while adding on to the extant literature.

1.4. Aims and Objectives

This current research aims to contribute to the domain of digital payment research while offering an extensive overview of research carried out in this domain. To achieve the aim of this research, the following research objectives have been framed.

- To explore the impact of digital payments on economic growth.
- To explore the impact of digital payments on rural development.
- To explore the impact of digital payments on business growth.

2. METHODOLOGY

The current study design will be systematic review and the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines will be used for conducting this review [19].

The Inclusion Criteria to be included in this systematic review are studies published between the periods of 2014-2022 should be considered. While studies which delved into the Indian context were included, many studies chosen revolved around global aspects were also included. Further, the studies published in leading peer-reviewed journals, and which are in English languages are to be reviewed.

The Exclusion Criteria to be considered to exclude a study from this review are the studies published prior to the period of 2014, studies that did not investigate digital payment adoption, or its impact on economy, rural development, book chapters, and conference papers. Studies published in mediocre journals or those that were found in grey literature or unpublished studies and that are not in English Language are to be excluded in the systematic review.

The search strategy adopted for this review was structured such that it considered peer-reviewed articles, those that were published with prominent journals. To facilitate this review, research papers between the periods of 2014 to 2022, those that were published in English will be considered. A Boolean search strategy would be adopted to obtain academic research articles. Appropriate keywords will be used to conduct a manual search, in tandem with cross-referencing strategy in place. Cross-referencing here would mean scouring the bibliography section of identified articles to find additional pertinent articles from those papers. The keywords that will be used would include digital payments, digital payment adoption, cashless transactions, technological development, mobile payments, economic growth, business growth, rural development, usage, consumer attitudes. Furthermore, keywords from identified papers would also be used to conduct further search. The search will be executed over leading databases like Scopus, Science Direct, Elsevier, Taylor and Francis, Web of Science, and JStor.

Data extraction will be carried out by retrieving all complete articles and those articles that match the inclusion criteria based on subject descriptors, titles and abstracts. Considering that the search strategy is also inclusive of cross-referencing, wherein bibliography from identified articles will be scanned and relevant papers chosen in case it adheres to the inclusion criteria defined.

Studies that are included in this review and used for data extraction would be extracted such that it is locally developed. The key elements that will be extracted from the selected papers would comprise of aspects such as; author, year, title, journal, objectives, methods, and findings. The articles thus derived through the search would be extensively reviewed with a view to facilitate a detailed and valid analysis.

Relevant articles were chosen for full-text screening after the application of the eligibility criteria. Article screening process and eligibility assessment process was carried out by the author. The articles were initially screened on the basis of their title, followed by the abstract of the article. In situations where the case titles and abstracts of the articles were irrelevant to the present investigation; these were excluded for the secondary screening. All analyses will be carried out based on previously published studies, and therefore, no ethical approval and patient consent will be required. Additionally, to prevent ethical issues with regards to plagiarism and copyrights, the findings from the selected articles will be duly paraphrased along with acknowledging the work of the authors via the addition of references.

3. RESULTS

PRISMA Chart

3.1. Eligible Studies

The literature search yielded 1454 articles from various databases including Emerald Insight, Ovid, Science Direct, Scopus, Web of Science, JStor and Google Scholar, of which 639 articles were excluded at the initial stage due to repetition and irrelevance. Out of 815, 597 articles were further excluded after analysis of the titles and abstracts at the first screening level.

A total of 218 potential relevant articles were selected for full-text evaluations, of which 196 articles were further excluded as the studies did not address primary endpoint (n= 93), and full texts could not be accessed (n=103), Finally, 22 studies meeting the inclusion criteria of the current systematic review as detailed in the PRISMA flow chart (Fig.1), were included in this research.

3.2. Impact of Digital Payments on Economic Growth

The study conducted by [20], interpreted the long-term association between long-term elasticity obtained from projected long-term coefficients from the ARDL model. It was found that the P-value of retail electronic payments were 0.000 with an elasticity of 0.2157. Based on the outcomes derived through the bounds test and projected long-term coefficient, it was fairly concluded that the retail electronic payments did not make any impact on the actual gross domestic product (GDP) over a long-term period. The author further added that within India, digital payments were measured through two key segments such as a) systematically importance financial market infrastructures (SIFMIs) and b) retail payments. SIFMIs comprised of real-time gross settlements (RTGS), and CCIL system of operation. Retail payments on the other hand comprised of retail electronic clearing, paper clearing, prepaid instruments of payment, and card payments as well. The findings derived from this study by [20][20], revealed that SIFMIs did not make any impact on the actual GDP of India. However, it was indicated that retail payments, particularly retail electronic payments like national electronic fund transfer (NEFT), national automated clearing house (NACH), Electronic Clearing Services (ECS), and Immediate Payment Services (IMPS), made a substantial short-term impact on actual GDP. Such avenues for electronic payments have acquired a prominence following the demonetization process and initiatives pertaining to ‘digital India’, driven by the Indian government have witnessed a healthy increase following the year 2014.

Over the long-term period, there is no impact that can be observed from retail electronic payments on the actual GDP of India. Thus, it can be said that digital payments mostly and retail electronic payments did not make any contribution to the economic growth of the country, in a direct manner, over a long-term period, and such payments might make an indirect contribution to economic growth through faster, lesser cost and convenient economic transactions.

A study was conducted by [21], the findings from which indicated that from the context of the recent COVID-19 pandemic, digital payments had a very special role to play in encouraging consumption across households and fostering sustainable economic development. The findings further indicated that digital payments made a substantial impact on consumer demand. The rapid development of digital payments within China in recent times, has had an obvious role to play in stimulating consumer demand, thereby encouraging sustainable economic development. Nonetheless, regarding time, there is no significant impact emerging from digital payments on consumer demands across several regions in China. This could be attributed to a small sample size that has been chosen. From a viewpoint of rural-urban variations, irrespective of whether in rural or urban regions, the impact of digital payments on consumption demand was obvious, and the impact on consumption expenditure in rural regions was higher as compared to consumption expenditure in urban regions. This is indicative of the fact that during the process of digital payment impacting consumer demand, the utility from rural regions are higher as compared to that of urban regions, which also indicated that the potential for rural consumption was higher in comparison with urban regions.

Based on an empirical study conducted by [22], the analysis of the data revealed that e-payments were extensively utilized by employees as compared to businessmen/women. From the findings, the authors also concluded that the use of e-payments overall in the Indian regions of Kolkata was comparatively higher than the region of Nagpur. However, the margin of variation was very small. The findings from the regression analysis on economic development arising from use of digital payments indicated an actual economic growth with the use of digital payments owing to the benefits it offered in terms of time and cost, increased transparency, and financial inclusion. A correlation analysis was instrumental in indicating that initiatives driven by the government of India were having a stimulating impact on people across the regions of Nagpur and Kolkata, for utilizing digital payments. In the same vein, the purpose of the study conducted by [23], was to obtain a detailed understanding about the association between electronic payments and economic growth across the world. Overall, it has been stated by the author that it was not possible to generalize findings around the world. Factors that were specific to each nation would have a role to play within this association. These included negative correlation ($r=0.7$) between POS terminals and GDP growth within Canada and Australia, however it was found to be positive for Saudi Arabia and the United Kingdom. For Saudi Arabia, a greater correlation coefficient between electronic transactions and GDP growth were found to be true for long and medium term however, in the case of Jordan, this relationship tends to become weak over a short-term period. Similarly, the study conducted by [1], indicated the correlation between increase in e-payments and growth in GDP. The authors suggest that the digital nature of money impacted the system of finances on the whole. Other than that, the use of cashless payment is intricately linked to the degree of economic growth. On one hand, an increased well-being level and development within the system of finances in developed nations stimulates transactions that do not involve cash. On the other hand, cashless payments have been found to be a major contributor in terms of accelerating economic development with the spread of electronic payments which can drive growth in consumption.

The findings from a study by [24] posited that a cashless economy was not simply an initiative driven by a government but rather it was a revolution that is necessary for making people comprehend and eventually empower them to accept and adopt digital transactions in their day to day lives. Nonetheless, shift to a cashless economy hinge on several factors where one of them would be the quality and availability of an appropriate telecom network. Based on a study conducted by [25], it was indicated that there was an evident regional imbalance within digital economy development within nations around the 'belt and road'. Particularly, Southeast Asia (Singapore), East Asia, Eastern and Central Europe had a comparatively higher level of digital economy, though several nations within West Asia (other than Israel), South Asia, and Central Asia, continued to lag. Also, the digital economy had a major positive impact on economic growth in nations along the 'belt and road'. It has the capability to drive economic growth by encouraging industrial structure upgradation, employment restructuring, and overall employment. Also, the findings presented through the study conducted by [26], showed that digital payments did make a huge impact, but it was not enough a switch to drive economic growth within a nation. The authors believed a larger usage needs to be facilitated which could drive general and economic growth across a nation.

3.3. Impact of Digital Payments on Rural Development

A study was conducted by [27], through which it was revealed that the use of mobile wallets was gaining much popularity, but its widespread adoption was being hampered by infrastructural issues within rural regions. For instance, rural regions were subject to extensive power cuts and load shedding, which hampered the adoption electronic payments or mobile wallets.

This caused people within rural regions to stick with conventional banking techniques. The findings further indicated that digital payments had much potential and could facilitate rural development if, the infrastructural aspects were taken care of. Similar findings were reported through the study carried out by [28], wherein it was revealed that citizens within rural regions were aware about digital payments, and they believed that use of such payment's mode would be fruitful. But they also added that this technique was highly intricate and involved a risk in functioning. Another challenge that hampered their technology adoption was that rural populace were unable to use it as they were not techno-savvy as 50 per cent of individuals from the study had basic school education. This could hamper adoption of digital payments and thus any scope for rural development as well. The findings from a study executed by [29], indicated a substantial association between digital payments and satisfaction from digital payments among people from rural regions overall, particularly during the time of the recent pandemic. The spread of the pandemic proved to be a watershed moment especially in the context of online payments in urban as well as rural regions. It acted as a turning point wherein digital payments emerged not simply as a safeguard for people in rural regions, but it turned out to be a way of life.

Another study conducted by [28], stated that the functions in digital payments need to be independent from the central banking utility of the reserve bank of India. The authors believed the key purpose of digitalization on rural banking comprised of protection of customers in the market for payments. Simply said, the customer must not be held responsible for any loss that might arise due to unlawful transactions or in case there is a failure in systems. The authors also add that there is high scope for the economy within rural regions to become cashless, however, appropriate steps need to be taken in this direction, which would drive rural development. Furthermore, [30] also add that more awareness about digital payments need to be created and there was also a need to improve financial literacy amongst rural population through diverse educational organizations or non-governmental organizations. The findings from a study conducted by [30], indicated that digital finance that was inclusive had a major positive role to play in terms of encouraging high-quality development within rural regions. This could be facilitated largely through the channel of economic efficiency, green ecological development, potential for innovative development, rural and urban structure, and harmony in the livelihood among individuals. Every single subdimension of digital finance that was inclusive positively impacted high-quality rural development to varying levels. There also existed a direct non-linear association among the key variables, that acted as a disincentive role to play during the initial phases and boost, following attaining a point of certain inflection. Therefore, the authors recommended the need to augment the development of high-quality infrastructure within rural regions, enhance the digitalization of inclusive finance by leveraging digital technologies like cloud computing, while widening the depth and breadth of inclusive digital financial services within rural regions, particularly in regions that were underdeveloped economically.

Similarly, the findings derived through a study carried out by [25], indicated that in the current phase, the digital economy has tremendous scope to offer novel opportunities to facilitate rural development. This can be done by effectively blending internet with a strategy for revitalization of rural regions, while speeding up the transition from conventional financial modes to contemporary modes in rural regions. The authors also add that agricultural products have largely depended on farmer's market to resolve channel challenges. Nonetheless, with the advent of new e-commerce mediums, people now have a 24-hour access to markets unrestricted by geographical boundaries or time. The study conducted by [31], indicated that the index of financial availability (IFA) within households in China continued to be at a low level. Though the availability of investments were quite low, there was high availability of bank loans.

The findings further revealed that in case digital payments were adopted within rural households in China, it could positively influence the IFA among households in rural China, and also the availability of bank loans, investments and private finance as well. This could eventually make a huge impact on rural development on the whole.

3.4. Impact of Digital Payments on Business Growth

[32] have found that digital payments that involved banks were advantageous in terms of productivity as well as profitability within commercial banks. Nonetheless, it is not possible to conclude the impact simply as negative or positive. Based on the kind of medium for digital payments, varied effects were observed from digital payments involving banks and third-party digital payment. The authors also added that developing digital payments presents threats as well as opportunities for conventional commercial banks. A similar study involving banks in Indonesia was conducted by [33], wherein the authors found that an equilibrium existed between digital payment transactions and long-term banking stability in the country. Additional investigation revealed a one-direction causality emerging through digital payments to stability in banking, and a positive short-term association among variables. Thus, it can be concluded that digital payments did have a positive impact on business growth from the context of banks.

Through the study executed by Uduji et al.(2018), it was found that mobile phone-based technology through the e-wallet programme in Nigeria was a vital aspect that improved farm business within rural regions in the country. Nonetheless, the findings also indicated that the influence of mobile phones (as a medium to use and access contemporary agricultural inputs) depended largely on the manner in which mobile networks were able to associate farmers who resided within rural regions and worked in the agricultural sector largely. Findings derived through a study carried out by Toriki et al.(2020), revealed that all indicators of electronic payments comprising of internet banking, POS machines, mobile bankings, cards, and ATMs made a positive impact on the performance of the financial sector which improves business growth. The findings also indicated that population and economic growth had a major positive impact on the performance within the financial sector. However, they also added that rate of interest and inflation could make a negative impact on it. Another study findings as derived on the basis of a study conducted by [34], emphasized upon the major association and direct impact between growth in sales and online shopping. At the same time, the results also confirmed indirect impact arising from online shopping and growth in sales via electronic payments. From this context, the results could be instrumental in identifying the impact of electronic payments on sales growth through online shopping, while also offering benefits, which would eventually result in business growth. The findings from a study by [35], have revealed that there was a significant and positive influence of e-commerce and electronic payments on performance within the MSME supply chains within Indonesia. The authors determined ten research indicators having low values, which presented a challenge to digitalization of MSMEs, and its implications, in terms of solutions and open innovation. The authors add that open innovation amongst MSMEs would prove to be beneficial in speeding up the process of digitalization amongst MSMEs within Indonesia. This could in turn spell growth of business through digitalization. Based on the study conducted by [36], it was indicated that utilizing Quick Response Indonesian Standards (QRIS) at the time of interactions among customers and business owners facilitates growth amongst culinary businesses, and it also makes a beneficial impact. Businesses as such are in a position to save on costs and time by enabling customers to scan a barcode. In addition, it was also found that QRIS enables business owners to maintain a record of their day-to-day income, while identifying products that are fast selling from their stock profiles.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings from the study carried out by [20], revealed that digital payments made a large impact on economic growth over a short-term period however, digital payments did not make any impact on economic growth over a long-term period. While extensive research has been carried out to investigate cause and effect associations while utilizing electronic payment modes and profitability of businesses, it has been evidenced that technologies facilitating electronic payments tend to boost profitability and productivity which augments economic growth [37](Rupashree et al., 2022; Vohnout et al., 2016). Similarly, findings from the study by [21], were also instrumental in indicating that digital payments were intrinsic to sustainable economic development. These findings were in tandem with the findings derived through the study conducted by [38], which indicated that digital financial inclusion could be beneficial in encouraging household consumption. Digital payments, buying financial products over the internet, acquiring online credit, and online shopping were the key intermediary variables of digital finance that impacted household consumption. Increase in household consumption would ultimately result in economic growth. In contrast to the above studies, the findings from the study by [23], indicated that there was no concrete evidence to either support or reject that there was any relationship between electronic payments and economic growth. The findings from the study by [39], indicated that there existed a robust correlation between e-payments augmenting the growth of GDP. This finding was in tandem with the study conducted by (Tee & Ong (2016), which indicated that there was a significant relation between digital payment adoption and economic growth. Another study conducted by [24], was in sync with findings derived through other studies, wherein it revealed that adoption of cashless payments had the potential to augment economic growth, while facilitating development within developing nations. However, the findings derived through the study by [23], posited that there could be different factors that impact adoption of digital payments and economic growth. Therefore, it was not possible to generalize the findings thus derived.

Though the findings that have been derived by [40], that digital payments were certainly beneficial but people in rural areas found it challenging to use technology due to limited education and technical skills. Similar findings were reported through the study conducted by [41], who stated that level of literacy impacted digital payment adoption which in turn could hamper the process of rural development. However, during the pandemic period it has been reported by [42], that digital payment technologies were not very difficult to use and required minimal educational levels. This was clearly evidenced during the pandemic when most people used digital payments to make online purchases. Favourable findings were reported through the study by [29], which posited that there was a substantial relation between digital payments and overall satisfaction among people from rural regions in times of the pandemic. As a matter of fact, the author has touted the pandemic that would prove to be a watershed moment for online transactions in rural as well as urban regions, which would effectively turn around the way business is being carried out and driving rural development. A study conducted by Singh & Malik (2019), presented detailed insights about digital technology adopted within rural regions, and outlined the perception and behaviour of rural customers to such services. The findings indicated that people from rural regions were enthusiastic about leveraging digital payments. As a matter of fact, it has been revealed through a study by [43], that the government in India is in the process of promoting Aadhar pay among the rural populace in India which would help users to conduct financial transactions using their fingerprints. This will also be instrumental in taking care of the issue of educational levels.

Findings from the study by [32], indicated that digital payments were instrumental in increasing productivity and profitability within commercial banks. Similar findings were reported through a study conducted by [44]. The authors found that digital payments played a crucial role not just in making GDP contributions, but it also was instrumental in modernizing economies, increase profitability and productivity, while also facilitate better public services through increments in tax-based revenues, thereby enabling business growth. [33] found an equal and long-term association between digital payment and banking stability, which facilitated growth of business. These findings were in tandem with the findings of a study by [45], who reported that financial inclusion and digital finance provided many advantages to users of financial services which could increase stability in the performance of an organization. However, both the studies have been conducted involving organizations in the finance sector, therefore, it would not be possible to generalize these findings to organizations in other industry sectors. While [46], believed mobile technology leveraging e-wallet programme was crucial in improving agricultural entrepreneurship in Nigeria. But at the same time the findings also indicated that mobile phones could only make an impact if mobile networks connected farmers residing in rural regions. Similarly, [47][48] reported a robust association between digital payments and business growth. However, no light was shed on whether mobile networks or connectivity had any adverse impacts. The findings from the study by [49], revealed that electronic or digital payments did positively influence business growth and productivity particularly in the financial sector. These findings were supported through the research presented by [50], who also indicated that POS transactions, and digital payments made a positive and substantial impact on return on assets within commercial banks in Nigeria. At the same time, [51][52] found that a negative impact was observed from RTGS on return on assets. Based on the study conducted by [35], believed there was an affirmative and substantial impact of e-commerce and e-payment service variables that drove the business performance of MSME supply chains within Indonesia. These findings were supported based on findings derived through studies by [53][54][51] who collectively found that positive outcomes could be derived when new technology encouraged the use of digital or electronic payment systems, which made a huge impact on the performance of SMEs.

5. CONCLUSION

Innovation in technology has brought in new dimensions in the global business scenario. But at the same time, efficient fund transfers are hampered by inefficient payment systems. This systematic review addressed several facets associated with digital payments. Mainly, it looked into how adoption of digital payments impacted economic growth, business growth and also how it facilitated rural development. The findings derived through this review indicated that adoption of digital payments did make an impact on economic growth, and business growth. However, as far as rural developments were concerned, it has been found that digital payments did have the propensity to impact rural development, but it has also been reiterated through studies that adoption of digital payments in rural areas might be restricted with lack of appropriate infrastructure, literacy level of rural populations, and issues in connectivity. These could certainly hinder the process of rural development with the adoption of digital payments. In future, quantitative research involving primary data is recommended to derive robust findings and to address gaps in current research.

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